

Preparation of yttrium barium copper oxide by polymeric precursor technique

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Manuscript received online 21 February 2012, revised 14 March 2012, accepted 26 March 2012

Abstract : Yttrium barium copper oxide has been prepared by polymeric precursor technique. Novelty of this work is the use of sodium polyacrylate which provides large number of -COO^- groups for binding polyvalent metal ions like Y^{3+} , Ba^{2+} and Cu^{2+} . After decomposing the polymeric part, XRD study has been carried out with the ash and it has been found that the product is yttrium barium copper oxide although BaO is mixed. Composition of the product may be controlled by controlling the amount of metal nitrate solutions which are mixed with aqueous solution of sodium polyacrylate to get the polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system. IR spectral study has been carried out to understand ion binding by the macromolecular system and thermal analysis has been carried out to understand thermal behaviour of these systems.

Keywords : Ceramic oxide, superconductor, sodium polyacrylate, polymeric precursors, X-ray diffraction.

Introduction

The discovery of superconductivity above the liquid nitrogen boiling point in Y-Ba-Cu-O system initiated important research. Preparation of ceramic oxide superconductor by citrate gel process has been reported¹⁻³. This motivated research on ion binding behaviour of guar gum-graft-acrylamide for polyvalent metal ions like Y^{3+} , Ba^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ³⁻⁵. This previous study indicates -COO^- group from the polymer is mainly responsible for binding polyvalent metal ions by guar gum-graft-acrylamide. So to bind Y^{3+} , Ba^{2+} and Cu^{2+} , a better choice may be sodium polyacrylate which will provide large number of -COO^- groups. In this present investigation, aqueous solution of sodium polyacrylate is mixed with $\text{Y}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solution, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution and pH of the mixture is raised by adding NaOH solution to get a precipitate which under suitable condition is collected and burnt at 1000 °C for 1 h to degrade polymeric part to get yttrium barium copper oxide. XRD study on the material obtained after decomposition shows, it is $\text{Y}_1\text{Ba}_2\text{Cu}_4\text{O}_8$ along with BaO. Preparation of yttrium barium copper oxide by polymeric precursor technique may be important from the point of view of processing of the material.

Materials and methods :

(i) Metal nitrate solutions :

$\text{Y}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solution or $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution is prepared by dissolving Y_2O_3 or CuO in nitric acid to get approximately 0.2 (M) solution. $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution has been prepared by dissolving $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in distilled water to get approximately 0.1 (M) solution.

(ii) Sodium polyacrylate :

Sodium polyacrylate used in this work has formula weight 201 to 300 (Brand : Aldrich and purity : 98%). The material is soluble in water.

(iii) Polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system :

50 ml approximately 3% sodium polyacrylate solution is mixed with 10 ml $\text{Y}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ solution, 35 ml $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution and 25 ml $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution and pH of the mixture is raised by adding 20 ml approximately 60% NaOH solution. A bluish precipitate is obtained. Mixture is allowed to stand for 15 min. Some amount of liquid is decanted off and then methyl alcohol is added. Whole mixture is allowed to stand for overnight. Colour changes from blue to grey. Maximum amount of methanol is removed by decantation. Mixture is allowed to stand

for decantation of liquid for several times. Then the mixture is allowed to stand for evaporation of liquid at room temperature for several days. Then it is allowed to dry in an oven. Mass is collected for IR spectral study, for thermal analysis and remaining amount is kept for burning to get yttrium barium copper oxide.

(iv) Preparation of yttrium barium copper oxide :

Remaining portion as mentioned above is used for burning in an oven at 1000 °C for 1 h in presence of air for thermal degradation of polymeric part to remove as CO₂ and H₂O. Remaining mass is used for X-ray diffraction (XRD) study to examine whether yttrium barium copper oxide has been formed or not.

(v) Instruments :

To record IR spectra of sodium polyacrylate and polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system, Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrometer (Spectrum RX1, SERIAL no. 73713) instrument has been used and KBr pellet technique has been adopted for IR spectral study.

Simultaneous DTA and TG analysis have been carried out using Perkin-Elmer (USA) Pyris Diamond TG/DTA instrument in presence of moisture free air. Heating rate was 10 °C/min.

XRD study has been carried out using X' Pert PRO (PAN Analytical Company, Holland) instrument by using powdered sample. Target : copper and detector : X' Celerator.

Results and discussion

Previously it has been found that aqueous solution of guar gum-graft-acrylamide binds Y³⁺ at pH near about 9.5, Ba²⁺ at pH near about 12.5 and Cu²⁺ at pH near about 6⁶. It has also been found that -COO⁻ group is mainly responsible for binding polyvalent metal ion by guar gum-graft-acrylamide³⁻⁵. That work indicated for binding Ba²⁺, very high pH is necessary. So to bind polyvalent metal ion by aqueous solution of sodium polyacrylate, 20 ml approximately 60% NaOH has been added to the mixture of aqueous solution of sodium polyacrylate, Y(NO₃)₃ solution, Ba(NO₃)₂ solution and Cu(NO₃)₂ solution.

IR spectra :

IR spectra for sodium polyacrylate and polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system are shown in Figs. 1

and 2 respectively. Peak at 1458.12 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of sodium polyacrylate can be attributed to -COO⁻ asymmetric stretch⁴. Peak at 1408.02 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of sodium polyacrylate can be attributed to -COO⁻ symmetric stretch. Peak at 1438.12 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system can be attributed to -COO⁻ asymmetric stretch. Peak at 1384.10 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra of polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system can be attributed to -COO⁻ symmetric stretch. These decrease in $\bar{\nu}$ values for polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system indicate macromolecular system is binding polyvalent metal ion.

Thermal analysis :

DTA and TGA plots for sodium polyacrylate are shown in Fig. 3. DTA and TGA plots for polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system are shown in Fig. 4. In DTA, the sample well is packed with the material to be tested and a second well is packed with the reference material that meets the criteria that it has no transition in the temperature range of interest. Reference material is alumina. The block is heated at a constant rate of 10 °C/min. The absolute temperature of the system and the differential temperature between sample and reference are recorded continuously. If the sample undergoes a transition at some temperature, a characteristic change in differential temperature is observed. Peak at 437.7 °C in DTA along with weight loss in TGA in the thermogram for sodium polyacrylate (Fig. 3) can be attributed to thermal degradation of the polymeric part. Similarly peak at 301.1 °C in DTA along with weight loss in TGA in the thermogram for polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system (Fig. 4) can be attributed to thermal degradation of the polymeric part. In the TGA thermogram for sodium polyacrylate (Fig. 3), there is negligible weight loss from 475.3 °C to 800 °C. But small change in weight from 423 °C to 800 °C in the TGA thermogram for polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system (Fig. 4), is probably due to formation of special oxide.

XRD :

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) pattern for the material obtained after burning the polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system at 1000 °C for 1 h, is shown in Fig. 5. Maximum peaks match with yttrium barium copper oxide and these peak positions are shown in Fig. 6. Al-

Fig. 1. IR spectra for sodium polyacrylate.

Fig. 2. IR spectra for polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system.

Fig. 3. DTA and TGA plots for sodium polyacrylate.

Fig. 4. DTA and TGA plots for polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular system.

Fig. 5. XRD pattern for material obtained after decomposing polymeric part.

Fig. 6. Positions of peaks in XRD, matching with yttrium barium copper oxide.

Fig. 7. Positions of peaks in XRD, matching with barium oxide.

though few peaks match with BaO and these peak positions are shown in Fig. 7. So the material is yttrium barium copper oxide (chemical formula $Y_1Ba_2Cu_4O_8$) and along with this BaO is mixed.

Conclusion :

Preparation of ceramic oxide superconductor by polymeric precursor technique is an important advancement in Materials Science. This work will open a new area in the preparation of ceramic oxide by polymeric precursor technique. Yttrium barium copper oxide prepared in this investigation contains barium oxide impurity. But barium oxide is soluble in water. So this problem may be removed by treating with distilled water. To control the stoichiometry of the oxide, proper control of amount of $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution, $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution and $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution to mix with aqueous solution of sodium polyacrylate, is necessary. This may be the fantasy of the process.

Acknowledgement

Authors acknowledge thanks to Dr. N. R. Jana and Dr. Durga Basak of IACS, Kolkata and Dr. P. Pramanick of IIT, Kharagpur for their help and co-operation to carry out this work.

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